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Making sense of the sustainable campus through student generated metaphors

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Abstract

Sustainable campuses are spaces where universities can contribute to a sustainable future by implementing environmentally, social, and economic principles. Nowadays, it is vital that campuses serve not only as centers of education but also as small cities that are the application areas of a sustainable mindset. Therefore, educational institutions should implement sustainable practices on campuses to fulfill their responsibilities to society and contribute to a sustainable future. The aim of this study is to examine the perceptions of students studying at two state universities in Konya, Turkey, regarding the concept of “sustainable campus”. In this study, metaphor analysis and semi-structured interview methods, qualitative methods, were used together. Combining these two methods provided an in-depth understanding of both conceptual and emotional dimensions. According to the metaphorical findings, participants associated the concept of a sustainable campus with environmental, economic, social, and cultural dimensions. Social sustainability was the dimension most frequently emphasized by the participants. Participants generally defined a sustainable campus with metaphors such as “nature” and “growth”, but they stated that they had difficulty producing metaphors due to the abstract nature of the concept. According to the interview findings, students had a general awareness of the concept of a sustainable campus, but this awareness was mostly limited to concrete practices such as environmental management and energy saving. Participants emphasized only the environmental aspects of sustainable campuses, whereas they did not have enough information about other aspects such as social and cultural sustainability. It was found that students, especially in engineering and technical departments, associate the concept of sustainability with infrastructure and energy efficiency, but have low awareness of the sustainability of social functioning on campus. The findings reveal that universities should not only limit the sustainable campus concept to environmentally friendly practices and develop policies to support social and cultural sustainability.

Keywords Sustainable campus, Sustainability, Metaphor analysis, Semi structured interview

1 Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a universal set of targets that address the complex interplay between social, economic, and environmental dimensions and aim to promote transformative change on a global scale [90]. These goals constitute both an analytical and normative approach to monitoring and evaluating progress in sustainability [49]. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) play a critical role in the implementation of this global sustainability agenda because of their role in knowledge production, dissemination and social responsibility [63]. The adoption of sustainability by HEIs involves not only technical practices to reduce environmental impacts but also a holistic educational approach that encourages students and other stakeholders to internalize sustainability principles and adopt sustainable lifestyles (Cotton et al., 2007). In this context, HEIs must ensure the commitment of all stakeholders to national and global sustainability goals and promote a deep understanding and adoption of sustainability concepts [17]. HEIs serve as important catalysts of societal change through knowledge generation, social development and innovation and can have significant impacts on local and regional economies [68]. Furthermore, HE institutions have the opportunity to contribute to policy-making processes through sustainability research and practice [110].

A sustainable university is defined as an institution that integrates sustainability principles into the core principles and operational principles of its educational activities and community engagement [84]. The primary focus of sustainable university campuses is the integration of sustainability principles into operational processes as well as educational and research activities. They take into account numerous factors related to carbon emissions, transformation, water, and energy management to reduce the environmental impact of all activities and ensure optimum efficiency in the use of resources by the university [34, 50, 80]. The provision of sustainable university campuses provides students with the opportunity to realize practical sustainability practices and theoretical knowledge. By directly interacting with environmental initiatives at their campuses, students increase their awareness of sustainability, thus increasing their potential to spread this awareness to the wider community.

The aim of this study is to contribute to the development of a new theoretical framework for sustainable universities in the context of integrating sustainability and campus life by introducing a new interpretation of the concept of sustainable universities from the perspective of university students. The literature review reveals that the concept of sustainable universities has been addressed within the framework of numerous theories [5, 25, 114]. The current study, like other sustainable campus studies in the literature that evaluate the campus as a system due to its structure [5, 83], tries to make a conceptual description from the evaluation of the students whom they consider as internal stakeholders. Systems theory is favoured to reveal the critical components of the sustainable campus concept [5, 120]. In particular, such methods are suitable for analyzing participants' thought structures, emotional reactions, and worlds of meaning. In this context, metaphor analysis and semistructured interview methods were preferred in our study to examine participants' perceptions of the concept of sustainable campuses.

Metaphor analysis is an effective tool for revealing abstract and conceptual connections in individual thought systems. The metaphors used by the participants concretize the perception of abstract concepts such as sustainable campuses and help us understand the implicit thoughts and worldviews related to these concepts [62, 67]. In

particular, this method analyzes individuals' mental models and identifies the aspects of the concept of sustainability that are emphasized more [16].

In contrast, semi-structured interviews allow the collection of both expected and unexpected data from participants with their flexible structure. This method, which progresses within the framework of pre-determined questions, can be adapted according to the participants' responses and allows for in-depth analysis [7, 56]. For example, open-ended questions about the perception of sustainable campuses allowed participants to focus not only on concrete issues such as environmental management and energy conservation as well as on social and cultural dimensions.

The combination of these methods enabled the detailed examination of complex social and individual processes. While metaphors revealed individuals' internal thought processes and social contexts, the interviews allowed these contexts to be evaluated from a broader perspective [31, 54]. In addition, the combination of these methods made it possible to understand individuals' perceptions of the concept of sustainable campuses not only at the individual level but also in the social and cultural contexts [36].

In this context, the present study seeks to contribute to the theoretical framework of sustainable universities by providing a student-centered interpretation of the sustainable campus concept. The aim is not only to generate strategies for sustainable university development and inform practical implementations, but also to provide a conceptual basis for future research. Qualitative methods—specifically metaphor analysis and semi-structured interviews—have been adopted to explore the multifaceted and abstract nature of the sustainability concept, allowing for a nuanced understanding of students' perceptions within their sociocultural contexts.

Building upon this methodological foundation, the primary aim of the study is to measure and understand the perceptions of students studying in different departments of two public universities in Konya regarding the concept of a “sustainable campus.” To guide this inquiry, the study is structured around the following research questions:

1. What metaphors have university students developed concerning the concept of a sustainable campus?
2. Into how many different categories can these metaphors be grouped?
3. What are university students' perspectives on the sustainable campus concept?

The combined use of metaphor analysis and semi-structured interviews ensures that both the symbolic representations and the articulated narratives of students are captured. This integration of qualitative methods reinforces the analytical rigor of the study and contributes to the broader discourse on sustainability in higher education.

2 Literature review

Studies on sustainable universities and campuses evaluate them from various perspectives. These studies, which are shaped within the framework of system, stakeholder and ecological modernization theories, have examined stakeholder perceptions in shaping sustainable universities and sustainable campuses, the regulation of administrative processes, systems acting together, social impact and collaborations. When the studies on students, which is the sample we take as the basis among these studies, are analyzed, it is seen that sustainability is shaped around the concept of 'green university campus.' In this framework, Abd-Razak et al. [1] evaluated students' perceptions of campuses'

physical structure. In this study, in which qualitative and quantitative methods were used together, survey data collected from 100 students at each university on the campuses of four state universities were evaluated. In addition, visual observations were made of the physical structures of the campuses, and evaluation notes were taken. The findings revealed the existence of similar problems at all campuses. The scope and severity of the problems differ. The most compact campuses were found to have the least problems affecting the physical life of students, and campuses should develop in this direction. Similarly, Abubakar et al. [3] investigated the components of a sustainable campus by surveying 152 students at the Faculty of Architecture and Planning, Dammam University, Saudi Arabia. The study revealed that despite students' awareness and concern about the environmental sustainability of the campus, there was a lack of interest and enthusiasm to follow developments in this direction. In particular, they emphasized the importance of providing incentives and training to help achieve a sustainable campus. This study is a number of studies that focused on the physical components of sustainable campus development. Walker and Mendler [111] presented an illustrative case study of a sustainable campus development project. This paper provides a comprehensive overview of Chatham University's Eden Hall Campus and its innovative sustainable design. In particular, the recently constructed Chatham University Eden Hall Campus, home to the Falk School of Sustainability and the Environment, is the first campus to be developed sustainably since its foundation in 2017. This campus is an immersive living and learning environment that will accommodate 1200 residential students and incorporates a range of sustainable features, including full-cycle water recycling, net positive energy generation, and zero waste operations. This paper analyses the key features of this campus and provides a definition of a sustainable campus.

Additionally, studies have been conducted that evaluate sustainability from a resource management perspective. In a study published in 2018, Alam examined the concept of green and sustainable campuses in the United States. A case study was conducted to evaluate universities in the research, whereby it was stated that although this concept is not new in the country's universities, there is a lack of publications and insufficient activities in comparison to its potential. The universities to be examined are those that have achieved platinum status according to the rating of the STARS evaluation organization. The evaluation will focus on the Stanford, California, Canada, British Columbia, and Canada Waterloo universities. While acknowledging the necessity for higher education campuses to adopt a variety of approaches, including physical changes in buildings and infrastructure as well as educational changes, to achieve sustainability goals, they proceeded to make a number of concrete recommendations that higher education institutions can undertake to achieve said goals [8]. In a similar vein, Ferreira et al. [44] explored the potential for added value through technical and organizational measures, without significant investments in energy and water savings, in the context of sustainable campus formation. Their findings indicated that an efficiency of over 20% in energy consumption and 58% in water consumption could be achieved through the implementation of a robust resource management policy. Ah et al. (2017) conducted research on university students in Malaysia. The data, which were collected from 216 undergraduate and 84 postgraduate students through the use of a questionnaire, indicated that while students are actively engaged in sustainable practices, it is necessary to implement continuous efforts to overcome the challenges that impede the promotion of a university-wide

culture of sustainability. Furthermore, the data from the survey demonstrated that in 2017, a considerable proportion of these students had adopted sustainable campus practices, including energy management, water conservation, the use of public transport, the effective management of waste, and active participation in recreational areas. The research yielded findings that were analogous to those of this study and explored campus initiatives on student practices, such as energy conservation, waste management, and public-transport use, with the objective of achieving sustainability goals.

Studies that adopt a similar approach to this research, namely a holistic evaluation of sustainability, are those that comprehensively examine the concept of sustainability. In their study, Abdulrazzaq et al. [2] developed a sustainable campus design model. The objective of this research was to ascertain the significance of stakeholders' lack of interest in the formation of sustainable campuses and to identify strategies for achieving such. This study put forth pivotal recommendations pertaining to the implementation of principles and standards for sustainable campus design, functional nodes, and comprehensive design. Additionally, a series of mechanisms were proposed to facilitate the realization of these recommendations. Chourey et al. [24] introduced their GRACIAS model, which stands for "Green Solution for Intellectually Conscious Sustainability on Academic Campuses." The model is designed to assist universities in achieving their sustainability objectives through incremental and quantifiable progress. It seeks to establish a sustainable campus environment in which human resources and environmental concerns are integrated. GRACIAS offers a comprehensive understanding of how universities can spearhead sustainability through structural alterations and a unified strategy and serves as a reference for universities in the effective implementation of sustainable practices. The objective of the study conducted by Carbon Neutrality target study was to identify the most prevalent sustainability initiatives undertaken by leading universities and to provide a framework for other institutions seeking to implement similar actions. The objective was to facilitate a more effective implementation of sustainability practices. In conducting this review, the activities were categorized into six main categories: transport, waste management, curriculum, food and catering, water and energy. By employing a quantitative assessment approach to the sustainability activities of universities around the world, a roadmap has been created with the data obtained, which can assist other higher education institutions in planning their next steps toward sustainability.

This study differs from existing studies in the literature that examine stakeholder perceptions of sustainable university and campus concepts in that it evaluates perceptions unfiltered. In addition, since it perceives the university campus as a whole, it analyses it in the context of system theory. Metaphor studies are studies that evaluate expectations and hopes about a concept without any guidance. To reach a conclusion from the research, a definition of the perceived components was created based on metaphors. Then, through structured interviews, the metaphors were further elaborated, and a projection of students' perceptions of sustainable campuses was created. The common denominator of the selected universities for the study is that they are located in a city in Turkey that aims to be carbon neutral. The Higher Education Council (YÖK), which acts as the upper body of universities in Turkey, established the "Sustainable and Climate-Friendly Campus Project" in 2022 and designated 11 universities as pilot institutions within this framework. According to the Paris Climate Agreement, which Turkey signed

in October 2021, Turkey announced a net zero emission target for 2053. In order to comply with initiatives such as the European Green Deal arising from the Paris Climate Agreement, projects that create tasks for institutions have been developed. This project is one of them. In cooperation with the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization, and Climate Change and the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources, roadmaps have been defined for these 11 universities to implement energy efficiency, renewable energy usage, zero waste practices, and environmentally friendly policies (YÖK, 2022). Selçuk University, selected within the sample, is one of the pilot universities. Additionally, Konya, the city where Selçuk and Necmettin Erbakan Universities are located, is one of the cities taking significant steps towards its vision of becoming a carbon-neutral city by 2042. In line with this goal, sustainable and environmentally friendly projects are being implemented in the city. For example, Turkey's first zero-carbon city library is being built in Konya (www.konhaber.com). The literature also shows that the industry of a city and its universities are significant actors in achieving their goals. Research has demonstrated that the lack of significant climate actions at the societal level poses an obstacle to urban sustainability. The multidimensionality of activities in higher education institutions, along with their interactions with different subsystems such as education, transportation, housing, and health, is considered a small model of cities. Furthermore, universities take on the role of contributing to and leading cities toward their sustainability goals through education, innovation, and research [9, 10, 12, 15, 53, 57, 60, 119].

When evaluated based on all these reasons, Selçuk University and Necmettin Erbakan University have also been included in the sample as elements that will contribute to the goal of carbon neutrality in Konya province. With this selected sample, one of the aims of this research is to evaluate the institutional structures of cities and universities in the context of a province in Turkey regarding the achievement of national sustainability goals and to fill this gap in the literature.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research methodology

The reason for choosing two qualitative methods as the research method is that qualitative research methods are considered appropriate for understanding abstract concepts and revealing the inner worlds of the participants [31, 33, 36, 121] (Patton, 2015). To achieve this, the metaphor and semi-structured interview methods were preferred.

Through metaphors, participants can associate a particular concept with more concrete and personal meanings, which allows the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of the topic [23, 62, 67, 91]. It also reveals the inner worlds of individuals and their emotional connection to the concept. Unlike traditional data collection methods, metaphor analysis offers participants a more creative and innovative form of expression, making the research process more interesting for both participants and researchers [28, 33, 62]. For example, an abstract concept such as “sustainable campus” can be understood through metaphors. Metaphors also reflect the participants' mental models, emotions, and experiences. This affords researchers a deeper understanding of how participants perceive and interpret the world. In this context, metaphor analysis is not only a descriptive tool but also a powerful method for understanding the dynamics of participants' mental models [58].

The semi-structured interview method was used to support and enrich the results of the metaphor analysis. Both methods are qualitative research techniques and offer the opportunity to collect and analyze data from different perspectives. Semi-structured interviews allowed researchers to have in-depth conversations with participants while maintaining a certain level of flexibility. Since this method has an open-ended structure, it allows participants to express their thoughts in their own words, which helps the researcher to collect richer and more detailed information about perceptions and experiences [31, 36, 56].

One of the most important advantages of semi-structured interviews is that they provide the researcher with a certain structure while, at the same time, offering flexibility. This method allowed the researcher to ask additional questions and collect more in-depth information based on the participants' responses [36]. Moreover, this process can be considered a process of constructing meaning through social interaction and allows participants to express their own perspectives more freely [31].

The combination of these two methods was preferred because it allowed the researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the participants' perceptions and the rationale behind these perceptions. In this context, methodological diversity increased both the data accuracy and analytical depth of the research [93].

3.2 Data collection process

Before collecting research data, ethical approval was obtained from universities, and participant consent was requested during the data collection phase.

As explained in Fig. 1, a mixed-method approach was preferred for the research roadmap. In this context, an online survey form containing the statement "A sustainable campus is like because" was first sent to participants for the metaphor method. The data collection process was completed in accordance with qualitative research methods to ensure diversity and representation.

Fig. 1 Research Roadmap

The number of participants was determined based on the “saturation point” principle recommended in qualitative research. According to this principle, the data collection process was concluded when the data obtained from new participants did not alter existing themes or categories [30]. The reasons provided by participants while generating metaphors were considered key elements in the metaphor analysis process.

A purposive sampling method was used for metaphor analysis. Purposive sampling was used to determine the most appropriate participants for the purpose of the research [81]. In this context, participants were selected from different academic disciplines and universities to reflect their perceptions of the concept of sustainability. Participants were recruited from two public universities (Necmettin Erbakan University and Selçuk University) in Konya, Turkey, and students were recruited from various faculties of these two universities, including social sciences, natural sciences, and health sciences. Diversity was considered both to provide an interdisciplinary perspective and to broaden the scope of the study.

Semi-structured interview questions were asked to the volunteer students who participated in the metaphor research. The interview questions were developed in line with the literature review and expert opinions to better understand the concept of a sustainable campus [56]. The interviews were conducted one-on-one and face-to-face, and an environment in which the participants felt comfortable was provided. In semi-structured interviews, participants were asked four open-ended questions to explore the concept of a sustainable campus in various dimensions. The collected data were analyzed by content analysis in accordance with qualitative research methods, and the perceptions of sustainability and the sustainable campus concept were categorized thematically.

The following interview questions were used:

1. What do you think about sustainability?
2. What do you think about sustainable campuses?
3. Did you encounter difficulties in producing metaphors for the concept?
4. What should your university do to create or develop a sustainable campus?

3.3 Coding process and determination of categories

3.3.1 Metaphor coding process and determination of categories

The classification of metaphors was carried out in more than one stage in accordance with qualitative data analysis. In the first stage, the metaphors created by the participants were described and recorded as direct statements. Then, these metaphors were analyzed in detail through content analysis, and recurring themes were identified. In the coding process, categories were created by considering the basic elements of each metaphor (e.g. “analogy” and “justification”).

In this process, the responses of the participants who expressed the concept of a sustainable campus with metaphors such as “rainforest” or “ecosystem” were categorized under distinct themes such as “nature”. This approach aimed to reveal the semantic contexts of the metaphors and emphasize their conceptual similarities.

The coding process included the following stages:

- (1) Data Preparation: Participants’ responses were transcribed.

- (2) Coding Process: Each metaphor was categorized according to a specific thematic meaning and grouped within the framework of recurring concepts, meanings, and relationships.
- (3) Determination of Themes: The metaphors identified during the coding process were combined under main themes such as environmental, social, economic, and cultural elements.
- (4) Verification with Expert Opinions: Expert opinions were taken regarding the accuracy of the metaphors and categories and the validity and reliability of the research.
- (5) Reporting the Results: The findings obtained from the thematic coding process were reported by supporting them with sample responses appropriate to the categories.

3.3.2 Interview coding process and categories determination

The data obtained from the semi-structured interviews were processed according to the principles of qualitative data analysis. The answers to the four main questions posed to the participants during the interview process were analyzed through thematic analysis. The coding process consisted of the following stages:

- (1) Recording and Data Transformation: The audio recordings obtained during the interviews were transcribed and transformed into raw data. The participants' answers were transcribed as individual statements.
- (2) Coding Process: The written texts were categorized based on the answers given to the questions. Frequently recurring themes and expressions were identified in the interview data, and these themes were coded to represent the participants' perceptions of sustainability and sustainable campus concepts.
- (3) Identification of themes: Four main themes were derived from the students' responses during the coding process:
 - Understanding Sustainability: Participants' understanding of sustainability in the context of environmental management, resource efficiency, and future investment.
 - Perception of a sustainable campus: Association of the campus environment with environmental and social responsibility.
 - Challenges in Metaphor Generation: Reflections on the Challenges Created by the abstract nature of the concept.
 - Recommendations for Universities: Participants' suggestions for solutions to make campuses more sustainable.
- (4) Validation with Expert Opinions: Expert opinions were considered to increase the validity and reliability of the coding process.
- (5) Reporting the Results: The findings obtained from the thematic coding process were reported by supporting them with sample responses appropriate to the categories.

The data obtained from the metaphor analysis played a decisive role in the interview preparation process. In particular, the themes emerging from the metaphor analysis were used as a guide for shaping the interview questions. For example, when recurring themes such as "resource conservation" or "environmental sustainability" were identified, participants were asked questions that deepened these themes, such as "What should your university do to become a sustainable campus?" during the interviews.

The main themes identified in the metaphor analysis were handled in a parallel structure during the analysis of the interview data, and the use of these methods together strengthened the internal consistency of the research. In addition, the contribution of metaphor analysis to the process of concretizing abstract concepts and expressing participants' perceptions made the interview data richer and more meaningful. This holistic approach enabled us to understand the participants' perceptions of sustainability and sustainable campuses in greater depth.

3.4 Validity and reliability

3.4.1 Metaphor analysis validity and reliability process

In qualitative data analysis, validity refers to whether the correct results are obtained in accordance with the purpose of the research, and reliability refers to whether these results are consistent [30]. To increase the validity of metaphor analysis, the contexts of the metaphors used should be correctly defined and classified. In this study, metaphors were analyzed using a content analysis method, and recurring themes were identified. The “simile” and “justification” elements of each metaphor were analyzed and categorized.

The following methods were applied to ensure validity:

- (1) Expert Opinions: To confirm that the metaphors were correctly categorized under the themes, 5 academicians who are experts in the field of social sciences were consulted, and the rate of consensus was calculated. Using the formula $\text{Reliability} = \frac{\text{Consensus}}{\text{Consensus} + \text{Disagreement}}$, a reliability rate of over 90% was reached [69].
- (2) Thick Description: A detailed description of the metaphors' context allows the reader to better understand and evaluate the findings [104].

Reliability was ensured through the following steps:

- (1) Multiple Coders: During the coding process, a second coding step was performed by an independent researcher, and the results were compared. High coding consistency strengthened the reliability of the study [64].
- (2) Utilizing Expert Opinions: The metaphors were re-evaluated and classified in line with the expert opinions. The reliability rate was calculated using the formula “ $\frac{\text{Agreement}}{\text{Agreement} + \text{Disagreement}}$ ” and was found to be above 90%. This high rate demonstrates the consistency of the coding process and the reliability of the results [69].
- (3) Transparency of the Coding Process: The coding process and results were reported in detail, which allowed other researchers to apply the same process and obtain similar results [95].

3.4.2 Validity and reliability of a semi-structured interview analysis

To ensure the validity and reliability of the interview process, it is necessary to carefully prepare the interview protocols and follow a systematic approach to data analysis. The interview questions were developed by considering relevant studies in the literature (Kvale and Brinkmann 61). Expert opinions were used to test whether the questions were comprehensible to the participants and appropriate.

The following methods were used to increase validity:

- (1) Data Triangulation: Interview findings were compared with those from the metaphor analysis, and validation was ensured. This method was used to test whether the findings obtained from different data sources support each other [81].
- (2) Detailed Explanation: During the interviews, participants' responses were transcribed verbatim, and the context of the responses was recorded in detail (Creswell, 2013). This process ensured that the findings could be verified by other researchers.
- (3) Coding and Theme Identification: The interview responses were analyzed using thematic analysis, and common themes were identified [20].
- (4) Expert Opinions: To confirm that the interview responses were correctly classified under the themes, 5 academicians who are experts in the field of social sciences were consulted, and the consensus rate was calculated. Using the formula $\text{Reliability} = \text{Consensus} / (\text{Consensus} + \text{Disagreement})$, a reliability rate of over 90% was achieved [69].

Reliability was ensured through the following steps:

- (1) Supervisory Coding: Support was received from another researcher during the coding process, and coding consistency was checked.
- (2) Data Intensive Use: Direct quotations based on the participants' statements were included in the report to support the reliability of the interview data [64].
- (3) Observer Consistency: Interviews were conducted by the same researcher to maintain consistency.

3.5 Limitations of the study

The findings of this study should be evaluated within the framework of the following limitations:

3.5.1 Sample numbers and characteristics

In this study, data were collected from 80 participants for metaphor analysis and 10 participants for semi structured interviews. Although the age range of the participants (18–26 years) and the diversity of their fields of study broadened the scope of the study, the total number of participants and age group may limit the generalizability of the results.

3.5.2 Geographical scope

This study is limited to data obtained from two public universities in Konya province (Necmettin Erbakan University and Selçuk University). Further studies in different cities or at the international level may better reflect cultural and regional differences in perceptions of sustainable campuses.

3.5.3 Methodological limitations

The research is based on metaphor analysis and semi-structured interviews, which are qualitative methods. While these methods are effective for understanding participants' perceptions in depth, the fact that the findings are not supported by quantitative analysis may make it difficult to generalize the results to a wider audience.

3.5.4 Data collection process

Data were collected through online questionnaires and face-to-face interviews with the participants. Data collection in an online environment may have prevented some participants from providing more detailed explanations due to technical limitations (e.g. access problems or inability to check responses).

3.5.5 Scope of the concept

The research focused only on the concept of “sustainable campus”. Expanding this concept and linking it to other dimensions such as sustainable universities and sustainable education could provide a more comprehensive framework.

3.5.6 Study area and participant diversity

The participants were from a variety of fields, such as social sciences, natural sciences, and health sciences; however, other disciplines (e.g. arts or engineering) may have been underrepresented. This may lead to a lack of diverse perspectives on sustainable campuses.

Despite its limitations, this study offers a unique perspective on the concept of a sustainable campus. Addressing the concept of a sustainable campus through metaphor analysis is a rarely used approach in the literature on this topic. This method enabled us to understand how participants perceived an abstract concept and how they related it to their experiences. In this respect, the study makes an innovative contribution to the literature. Moreover, the study is based on a sample of students in social sciences, natural sciences, and health sciences. This diversity allows us to understand how individuals from different disciplines approach the concept of sustainable campuses. This distinguishes studies from those that focus on a single discipline. Finally, the study contributes to both local and international literature by addressing a universal concept, namely, sustainability, in the Turkish context. In this respect, the findings of this study can provide a basis for comparison with other cultures and contexts.

4 Research results

4.1 Demographic information about the participants

The number of participants who voluntarily participated in the metaphor analysis was 80. Of the 83 participants, 54.2% were female and 45.8% were male. The ages of the participants were between 18 and 25. 35 of the participants are students of Necmettin Erbakan University, and 45 are students of Selçuk University (both universities are located in Konya). The participants' fields of study included Management Information Systems, International Trade and Finance, Computer Engineering, Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Agricultural Engineering, Business Administration, International Relations, Painting, Fashion Design, Psychology, Law, Veterinary Medicine, Art History, Teaching and Medicine. Thus, students in social sciences, natural sciences, and health sciences contributed to the diversity and scope of the research.

A total of 10 students voluntarily participated in the semi-structured interview. Their ages ranged from 20 to 26 years, and their majors included Philosophy, Literature, German Language, Child Development, History, Agricultural Machinery, Fashion Design, Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, and Physical Education Teaching. Six of the participants were female, and four were male. According to the university distribution, 6

participants are studying at Selçuk University and 4 participants are studying at Necmettin Erbakan University.

4.2 Metaphoric analysis findings

For metaphor analysis, an online survey form containing the phrase “A sustainable campus is like Because” was prepared and sent through email and social media accounts. Participants who wished to participate voluntarily responded, and the data obtained were tabulated using descriptive analysis. The Table 1 shows the results of the metaphor analysis.

According to Table 1, the participants produced 42 metaphors related to the concept of a sustainable campus. These metaphors are associated with four different categories. These categories overlap with the sustainability literature. Sustainability is examined in four main contexts: economic, environmental, social, and cultural [21, 39, 115].

The environmental sustainability category included metaphors such as being in touch with nature, rainforests, trees, and ecosystems, and this category represented 21.42% of the metaphors and 32.5% of the participants. Economic sustainability was expressed with concepts such as continuity of resources, investment, and power and was emphasized by 16.66% of the metaphors and 11.25% of the participants. Social sustainability was associated with concepts such as life, peace, breath, hope, and meditation, and this category was the most frequently used, representing 38.09% of the metaphors and 40% of the participants. Cultural sustainability was defined using metaphors such as cleanliness, mother, heaven, cultured, human, home, and utopia; this category covered 23.8% of the metaphors and 16.25% of the participants. The findings revealed that the students used metaphors belonging to the social sustainability category more frequently compared to the other categories, and their perceptions of this category were stronger.

4.3 Interview analysis findings

The answers given by the participants to the questions in the interviews conducted with a total of 10 students studying in various departments from two different universities are given in Table 2.

Table 1 Metaphoric analysis findings

Categories	Relevant Methaphors	Number of meta-phors (n)	Per-centage (%)	Num-ber of People (n)	Per-centage (%)
Environmental Sustainability	Being in touch with nature, rainforests, nature, forest, trees, area where there is more tree planting than construction, it is like a part of the ecosystem, the smell of flowers, spring, it is like a key for the environment, environmentally friendly	9	21,42	26	32,5
Economic Sustainability	Continuity of resources, development, university, productive tree, future, very strong investment, like a toddler.	7	16,66	9	11,25
Social Sustainability	Life, peace, breath, hope, meditation, oxygen, serotonin, life, balance, a free space where we can express ourselves, a peaceful home of knowledge, peace, a living space—it is like the existence of the infinity of the heavens on earth, happiness.	16	38,12	32	40
Cultural Sustainability	Cleanliness, mother, heaven, cultured, human, home, utopia, youth, truth.	10	23,8	13	16,25
Total		42	100	80	100

Table 2 shows that the responses of the students who participated in the interviews were evaluated using the content analysis method. In this analysis, four basic interview questions were considered, and the students' perceptions of the concept of sustainability, understanding of sustainable campuses, and their suggestions were classified thematically. The interview results were evaluated according to the following main themes:

Theme 1: Understanding sustainability

The responses indicate a broad but somewhat limited understanding of students' sustainability. Most participants associate sustainability with environmental management and resource efficiency. For example, participants from the Philosophy and Literature departments of Selçuk University emphasized the importance of balancing the use of natural resources and minimizing environmental impacts. This reflects a general awareness of the environmental dimensions of sustainability and is in line with the widespread interpretations of the concept in the academic literature.

However, there are also gaps in knowledge. For example, some students, such as those from the Agricultural Machinery department, openly admit their lack of understanding of sustainability. This situation indicates the need for more comprehensive education on sustainability issues in university curricula, especially in non-environmental disciplines.

Theme 2: Perceptions of a Sustainable Campus

The concept of a sustainable campus was generally accepted, although interpretations varied. Students frequently mentioned that environmental elements such as energy efficiency, waste management, and green spaces were integral parts of a sustainable campus. A student from the German Language and Literature Department at Necmettin Erbakan University emphasized maintenance and diversity by likening a sustainable campus to a "garden," metaphorically representing the ongoing efforts required to maintain sustainability.

Interestingly, as one PE student noted, the idea of a sustainable campus as a system that supports and motivates students adds a social dimension to the concept by emphasizing the role of the campus environment in fostering a supportive community.

Theme 3: Difficulties in Generating Metaphors

Many students struggled to create metaphors for sustainable campuses, indicating that the concept is abstract and not easily conceptualized. Those who created metaphors often associated them with nature and growth. For example, a participant from the Child Development Department at Selçuk University compared a sustainable campus to "greenery," reflecting an intrinsic connection to nature. Another student compared it to a "sapling," symbolizing growth and future potential. These metaphors suggest that students perceive sustainable campuses as living, growing entities that require maintenance and have the potential to provide significant benefits over time.

Theme 4: Recommendations for Universities

Participants made a variety of actionable suggestions on how their universities could be improved. Common suggestions included investing in renewable energy, improving waste management, increasing green spaces, and promoting environmental education. These suggestions reflect a holistic approach to sustainability that recognizes the need for both infrastructure and educational initiatives. Students from the History and Metallurgy departments also emphasized the importance of engaging the community, such as collaborating with local farmers or promoting public transportation, which aligns with

the broader concept of sustainability, which includes social and economic dimensions as well as environmental considerations.

5 Discussion

This study examined university students' perceptions of the concept of a sustainable campus using qualitative research methods. The findings revealed that students approached the concept of sustainability in a multidimensional manner and were aware of sustainable practices on campuses. In this study, metaphorical and semi-structured interview methods were employed as qualitative methods. Therefore, the research results are discussed based on the data obtained by the two methods.

First, as a result of the metaphor analysis, the university students produced 42 different metaphors. These 42 metaphors were presented in a descriptive analysis under four categories, considering the relevant literature.

It is seen that students' environmental attitudes have a strong effect on their perceptions of sustainability [85, 99]. In the study, it was determined that students generally produced metaphors that established a strong relationship with nature, ecosystem and environment in the category of environmental sustainability. This shows that students perceive the concept of sustainability in the context of environment and ecosystem. The findings are in parallel with the studies conducted by Wang et al. [112, 113], which emphasised the importance of environmental sustainability in campus life. However, in the current study, it was observed that metaphors for environmental sustainability were less emphasised than social and cultural sustainability. This finding suggests that students consider sustainability with a focus on the environment, but they keep this dimension in the background compared to other sustainability components.

It is stated that students' attitudes towards environmental sustainability contribute to effective business decision-making processes related to organisational environmental goals [99]. However, it is stated that students' attitudes towards environmental sustainability have not been sufficiently analysed in the relevant literature. In the literature, it is emphasised that individuals' perceptions of sustainability, especially in developing countries, mostly focus on economic and social dimensions [37]. In this context, the fact that students are less inclined towards the environmental sustainability category in metaphor formation processes suggests that sustainability is evaluated in a more pragmatic framework in terms of individual and collective benefit [46].

Students' ecosystem and nature-based conceptualisation of environmental sustainability may reflect the influence of curricula focused on environmental education and sustainable development [79]. However, this trend also reveals the need to increase awareness of the fact that environmental sustainability is not limited to the protection of nature, but also includes an integrated structure with socio-economic systems [115]. Therefore, it is important to address environmental sustainability with a more holistic approach and to convey it to students in a way that includes all dimensions of sustainability.

It is seen that the metaphors produced by students in the economic sustainability category generally focus on the concepts of continuity of resources, investment and power. However, this category stands out as the area with the least number of metaphors in the study. This shows that students prioritise the economic dimension in the concept of sustainability less than other categories and have difficulty in making sense of it.

Table 2 Interview analysis findings

Participants	University	Department /Class	What do you think about sustainability?	What do you think about sustainable campus? What do you think a sustainable campus resembles/is like? Why?	Did you encounter difficulty in generating a metaphor for the concept?	What should your university do to create or develop a sustainable campus?
Participant 1	Selcuk University	Philosophy/4th Year	"In my opinion, it is to use natural resources in a balanced way to meet future generations' needs. To be sustainable, environmental impacts must be minimized. Sustainability is important when it is necessary to take responsibility for the environment and society	"Sustainable campuses encourage environmentally friendly practices. They are campuses that embrace sustainability principles. Institutions should instill sustainability awareness among students and staff. Sustainability is necessary to leave a more livable world for future generations. Therefore, it is valuable for future generations. It grows like a sapling. Because it provides roots and strengthens to meet the needs of the society. It gives hope for the future	"I had a hard time	"Investment should be made toward renewable energy sources. People should be encouraged to use water effectively. Environmentally friendly products should be preferred on campus. Information on sustainability should be provided because no one knows about it. People should be made aware of this issue and precautions should be taken
Participant 2	Selcuk University	Literature/ 4th Year	"I don't know much about sustainability, but I believe it is an important concept for future generations	"The first thing that comes to mind is environmental education and projects for the community. It could raise awareness; it could operate without harming the environment. "A sustainable campus is everything that constantly grows and develops."	"I had difficulty generating a metaphor on this topic."	"In order for my university to be a sustainable campus, it should cooperate with farmers. It can supply organic food from them. I think they have departments and professors to do this. The university should encourage departments in this regard
Participant 3	Necmettin Erbakan University	German Language and Literature/4th Year	"In my opinion, sustainability refers to the effective management of natural resources, taking into account the needs of future generations. In order to control our future, we need to be sustainable	"In my opinion, a campus is a place where environmental and social responsibilities are implemented in addition to educational and training activities. These campuses can be leaders in areas such as energy efficiency, waste reduction, social participation, and environmental protection. "I think a sustainable campus is similar to a garden. Because both require constant maintenance. And it serves as a resource for society. Because we cannot be sustainable without our garden. It encourages diversity and productivity. It gives people peace and vitality	"In other words, it was an abstract concept, and I had a hard time concretizing it. It was difficult to find a metaphor that accurately represented this concept	"My university is not doing anything to make its campus sustainable." I think they can take various steps to do so. They provide energy efficiency. They can manage waste because there is a lot of environmental waste in the university. Environmental education and awareness can be provided. It would be beneficial to encourage social participation in this regard. I think it is important to create a culture of sustainability

Table 2 (continued)

Participants	University	Department /Class	What do you think about sustainability?	What do you think about sustainable campuses? What do you think a sustainable campus resembles/is like? Why?	Did you encounter difficulty in generating a metaphor for the concept?	What should your university do to create or develop a sustainable campus?
Participant 4	Necmettin Erbakan University	Child Development/1st Year	"Natural resources are being used to meet today's needs." We should consider future generations' needs by addressing issues like the environment, nature, economy, and social surroundings while preserving these resources. I can say that it ensures the long-term well-being of society	"A sustainable campus is actually a good thing, but if I consider my own university, unfortunately, I don't think they are sufficient. Whether it's the trash around, education, or the economy, I don't think it's good." A sustainable campus is similar to an ecosystem, in my opinion, because both sides should be kept balanced. When changing a part, you should consider that it will affect the others	"It is impossible not to have difficulties."	"Wherever we look, we see garbage. First, garbage and waste processes can be performed. Campaigns can be organized on this issue. The welfare of our university and our environment can be provided
Participant 5	Necmettin Erbakan University	History Department, 4th year	"The first thing that comes to mind is the next generation. We must leave a better world for the next generation. Another issue I think about is environmental awareness, resource efficiency, and social welfare	"When I say sustainable campus, the first thing that comes to mind is students and staff. Because it aims to prepare a more livable world for them. It encourages environmental sustainability." I think a sustainable campus is like nature. Because nature meets human needs, a sustainable campus meets our needs	"To be honest, I had a hard time. Because I did not have much knowledge of the subject	"I would like to give a few examples from what I have seen around me. Green areas can be protected, and landscaping applications can be implemented. Bicycles can be used for transportation. Bicycle parks can also be built. Public transportation is encouraged rather than private vehicles. Subject-based training can be provided. It is important to provide training on the subject because I was even able to learn something thanks to this meeting. We are all very deficient in this regard
Participant 6	Necmettin Erbakan University	Agricultural machinery/3rd grade	"I have no knowledge about this subject."	"This is the first time I have heard of a sustainable campus."	"I had a hard time."	"They need to be more careful about their environment." Renewable energy sources should be used

Table 2 (continued)

Participants	University	Department /Class	What do you think about sustainability?	What do you think about sustainable campuses? What do you think a sustainable campus resembles/is like? Why?	Did you encounter difficulty in generating a metaphor for the concept?	What should your university do to create or develop a sustainable campus?
Participant 7	Selçuk University	Child Development Department, 2nd year	"The environment comes to mind."	"It is a campus concept that is beneficial to nature." "A sustainable campus is similar to green because it is intertwined with nature."	"I had a hard time."	"More green areas and flower gardens can be built on the campus. Flowers can also be planted. We can be more sensitive about waste"
Participant 8	Selçuk University	Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, 2nd year	"Nature is the relationship between the environment and humans."	"It is an active campus where students are intertwined with nature." "A sustainable campus is like a clean and spacious campsite where nature and greenery come together. Greenery and the environment are essential for humans. It gives us peace"	"I had some difficulty."	"It can do more afforestation and landscaping."
Participant 9	Necmettin Erbakan University	Physical education teacher 1st year	"I think it is an investment in the future and should be done."	"A sustainable campus is a system that motivates students." "A sustainable campus is a development because it is future-oriented."	"I had a hard time."	"They can create natural areas where students and staff can spend time."
Participant 10	Selçuk University	Fashion design department/1st year	"It is an investment in the future"	"Sustainable campus is a positive area to spend time." "Sustainable campus is similar to a gain (it is a gain). Because the return is positive. It creates positive effects"	"I had a hard time."	"They can create refreshing, green areas. They should educate students and staff on the subject. Green campuses are not a very well-known concept for us."

The findings are consistent with studies by Ribeiro et al. [87, 88], who found that students make less sense of economic sustainability compared to environmental and social dimensions. The authors state that economic sustainability is overshadowed by environmental and social sustainability in terms of educational context and general awareness [87, 88].

The fact that students conceptualise economic sustainability mostly through the continuity of material assets and financial mechanisms indicates that this dimension carries a more abstract structure in their minds compared to concrete environmental and social sustainability elements [86]. There may be several reasons for this situation. Firstly, sustainability education programmes predominantly focus on environmental and social issues, while the economic dimension is relatively less emphasised in educational processes [98]. Economic sustainability is usually elaborated in the disciplines of business and economics and is treated as a secondary component in environmental science or social science curricula [66]. In addition, economic sustainability is inherently more abstract and systemic in nature, making it difficult for students to grasp [13]. Sterling [98] argues that the education system generally presents sustainability in terms of the environmental dimension and economic sustainability is addressed in a superficial framework such as 'financial success'. Therefore, economic sustainability needs to be addressed more comprehensively and students need to be provided with an educational perspective in which they can grasp the critical role of this dimension in sustainable development.

The most represented category in the study was social sustainability. The prevalence of positive and human-centred metaphors such as life, peace, breath, hope and meditation shows that students evaluate the concept of sustainability within the framework of social relations, social harmony and individual welfare. This category, which includes 38.09% of the metaphors and 40% of the participants, reveals that students primarily associate sustainability with its social dimension. This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Msengi et al. [71, 72], who stated that social sustainability is perceived as a fundamental element of campus life.

There may be several reasons why students make more sense of social sustainability than other dimensions. Firstly, since university environments encourage interpersonal interaction and collective learning, students may consider sustainability as a more prioritised issue in the context of social dynamics [102]. Social sustainability is directly related to concepts such as equality, solidarity and social cohesion to improve the quality of life of individuals [32]. In this direction, metaphors such as peace, breath, hope and meditation developed by students reveal that sustainability is not only an ecological and economic concept, but also has a strong connection with human psychology and social relations [46].

In addition, today's global social crises-factors such as pandemics, economic uncertainty, and migration movements-have made social sustainability more visible [105]. In this context, it is likely that students tend to consider sustainability primarily from their own life experiences and social context rather than from an environmental or economic perspective [70]. This can be explained by the fact that social sustainability is a concrete dimension that individuals can directly experience in their daily lives.

In the study, students produced metaphors such as cleanliness, mother, heaven, cultured, human, home, utopia, youth, and truth under the category of cultural

sustainability. These metaphors show that students consider sustainability not only in terms of environmental or social dimensions, but also in the context of cultural heritage and social belonging [38]. Cultural sustainability was the second category with the highest number of metaphors after social sustainability. This finding shows that students see cultural values and traditions as an integral part of sustainability and develop awareness of how these values are integrated into campus life.

While students' perception of cultural sustainability as an important dimension reflects their level of awareness on this issue, the fact that it is less dominant compared to social sustainability can be explained by the fact that interpersonal relationships and social structures affect students' daily lives more directly [38]. Adams et al. [4] study also supports these findings and emphasises that cultural change is critical for sustainability.

Cultural sustainability refers to the process by which societies preserve their identities, traditions, languages and values and pass them on to future generations [96]. The metaphors of mother, home, paradise and utopia produced by the students can be associated with the sense of belonging, security and the continuity of cultural values from the past [101]. The metaphors of cultured and human reveal the role of social education and interpersonal communication in the continuity of social sustainability [77]. On the other hand, the metaphor of cleanliness suggests that there is a moral and ethical dimension in the perception of sustainability [51].

As a result, although students see cultural sustainability as an important component, they do not internalise it as strongly as social sustainability. The main reason for this is that social sustainability directly affects the daily lives of individuals, while cultural sustainability has a broader scale and long-term perspective. Making cultural sustainability more visible through educational programmes and practices on campus can be effective in increasing students' awareness of this dimension (Fig. 2).

The results of the semi-structured interview analysis reveal that students studying in different disciplines do not have sufficient knowledge about sustainability and sustainable campus concepts (Fig. 3). This finding coincides with the views frequently discussed in the literature that sustainability education is not sufficiently disseminated in higher education institutions [65, 117]. Participants consider the concept of sustainable campus mainly in the context of social and environmental sustainability; however, they clearly state that they find their universities' efforts in this field insufficient. This can be explained by the limited access of students to sustainability education and the lack of sustainability themes in the curriculum [14].

Research findings show that university students' perception of sustainability is generally limited to environmental sustainability (Emanuel & Adams, 2011). Sterling [97] states that traditional education systems are far from addressing the concept of sustainability in a holistic framework and therefore, students associate sustainability with environmental factors that they feel the direct impact of. Similarly Clugston and Calder [26, 27] emphasise that sustainable campus initiatives should receive high-level support from

Fig. 2 Venn diagram of the metaphors

Fig. 3 Venn diagram of interviews

university administrations. Without such support, it is not possible for students to gain an effective understanding of sustainability.

Most of the participants pointed out the importance of energy efficiency, waste management, increasing green areas and educational programmes that promote environmental awareness in order to create sustainable campuses. These findings are consistent with the view put forward by Velazquez et al. [106] that sustainable campuses are shaped around elements such as energy efficiency, green space management, waste reduction and sustainable transport. However, for these initiatives to be successful, students need to actively participate in the process and university administrations need to prioritise these issues [26, 27]. Sustainability should be assessed not only through investments in physical infrastructure, but also through the level of knowledge, skills and awareness gained by students [14]. Universities 'holistic approach to sustainability education will contribute to students' understanding of sustainability from a broader perspective.

The interview findings show that engineering students tend to evaluate the concept of sustainability predominantly in a concrete and technical framework. This can be explained by the fact that engineering education focuses on measurable, applicable and technical processes [73, 92]. However, contrary to expectations, it was observed that engineering students do not have sufficient knowledge about sustainability. This result is distortive and suggests that this concept is not addressed holistically enough in the education process. Current curricula prioritise technical skills and do not adequately incorporate the interdisciplinary and ethical dimensions of sustainability [22, 65]. This finding is in line with existing criticisms of sustainability education; Sterling [97] states that traditional engineering education systems limit sustainability only to technical applications, making it difficult for students to evaluate this concept from a broader social and ethical perspective. The views that engineering education should be developed within the framework of sustainability are also supported by criticisms that engineering curricula focus on technical and scientific content while leaving ethical, social and economic dimensions in the background [43, 92]. Indeed, a study conducted by Segalas et al. [92] revealed that engineering students' sustainability awareness is generally limited to environmental and technical aspects, but they give less importance to social and governance dimensions. Byrne et al. [22], on the other hand, state that engineering students can only

make sense of sustainability in the context of engineering projects, but they do not sufficiently comprehend broader social and cultural impacts.

At this point, the role of universities in sustainability education is of critical importance. While Cortese [29] emphasises that sustainability education should be integrated with different disciplines such as engineering, social sciences, management and environmental sciences, Lozano [65] states that interdisciplinary learning environments should be encouraged. Sustainability in universities should not be limited to physical infrastructure arrangements, but should be made a part of students' academic experiences [26, 27]. In this context, Disterheft et al. [35] state that designing sustainability policies in a way that encourages the active participation of students in universities plays a critical role in terms of raising awareness in the long term.

The research findings also show that students perceive sustainability largely in a social context. The fact that social sustainability is the most frequently emphasised category reveals that students prioritise social welfare, equality and social justice in their perception of sustainability. While Dempsey et al. [32] emphasise that social sustainability is directly linked to urbanisation, education and social welfare, Boström [18] states that sustainability is better understood when focusing on how it has an impact on improving the quality of life of individuals and social justice. These findings suggest that the social dimension should be emphasised more in sustainable campus policies. Increasing social sustainability practices on campus can contribute to students' deeper understanding of the concept of sustainability and its application in their daily lives [102].

6 Conclusions

This study examined university students' perceptions of the concept of sustainable campuses. The findings revealed that although students consider sustainability in the environmental, economic, social, and cultural dimensions, their awareness levels regarding these dimensions vary.

Recent studies have shown that very few universities have sufficient practices and activities to make their campuses sustainable [94, 100]. However, universities are the segment of society with the most access to the intellectual capital required to provide sustainable practices and measurements [94]. Despite this, there are major obstacles to sustainable campuses. The biggest obstacles to campuses adopting these practices include a lack of sufficient knowledge about the subject and reluctance to make commitments regarding environmental protection [45].

Sustainable campuses not only promote environmental sustainability but also integrate it into education and management processes by fostering a green culture in universities. This culture covers various areas, from management to education and activities [112, 113]. Murray [74] revealed that when students understand the importance of sustainability initiatives, they can ensure that such initiatives are successful. Wu [118] found that university students are more likely to contribute positively to sustainability efforts on campus when they actively participate. Msengi et al. [71, 72] revealed that although students recognize the importance of sustainability, most are unaware of their universities' sustainability commitments or initiatives. Therefore, universities have a lot of work to do. Indeed, the university students who participated in the study emphasized that they did not receive training in this area and that activities were limited. Gandasari et al. [45] also supported the results of this study. Individual awareness needs to be increased to

implement the concept of a green campus. Trainings for this purpose play an important role in creating environmental awareness and encouraging sustainable practices [41].

To be a sustainable campus, it is necessary to act in a green way. Indicators such as green consciousness, attitude, and behavioral control stand out as the basic elements of green behavior [40]. In their answers to the interview questions, the students emphasized the necessity of acting green. To be a sustainable campus, universities must first act green and spread sustainability awareness throughout the campus.

Sustainability initiatives cannot be successful without top-level support. Managing resources such as energy and water efficiently, reducing waste, and promoting sustainable transportation options on campus should be seen as key strategies for university administration [26, 27].

Eco-plus culture is another element that can contribute to the establishment of a sustainable perception in the behaviour of individuals. Eco plus culture is a system that can be activated by methods adapted to the ecological system and feeds it with cultural values (Nguyen,2024). The formation of a system that will motivate students' perceptions and willingness to transform their behavior requires the reinforcement of acceptance or rejection of environmental values, as well as the awareness of sustainability as a threshold value. An effective information processing mechanism at both individual and societal level can thus contribute to the development of a progressive environmental values system [107].

Integrating sustainability into the curriculum is crucial. Sustainability topics should not only be included in courses but should also be embedded across disciplines so that students from a variety of disciplines can understand its importance. They should also work with local communities to extend sustainability efforts beyond campus and help create a broader impact. Universities should not only conduct research on sustainability but also apply these findings to their own activities and share them with the broader community [26, 27].

Adams et al. [4] stated that universities focus solely on curriculum and technical solutions when it comes to sustainability, ignoring culture. According to the authors, one of the prerequisites for creating a sustainable campus is cultural change. Cultural change is critical to sustainable initiatives' long-term success.

Many students see sustainable campuses as beneficial to the environment and a positive reflection of their university's commitment to global issues. The presence of green spaces, energy-efficient buildings, and sustainable transportation options are generally appreciated by students. However, as in this study and others [71, 72], students know that unless there are educational and promotional programs, they do not have an understanding of how sustainability is implemented on campus and that integrating sustainability into the curriculum is crucial. Too and Bajracharya [103] found that students who feel involved in their university's sustainability initiatives are more likely to participate in and support these efforts. Pereira Ribeiro et al. [87, 88] argued that sustainable campus practices enable students to demonstrate a higher level of proactivity and awareness of sustainable development. Therefore, the concept of a sustainable campus should be seen as important as it serves to bring the sustainability dimensions of universities to life through research, teaching, and practice.

6.1 Recommendations

The recommendations presented in this section are structured based on the findings of the study. The recommendations are divided into two main groups: researchers who contribute to the development of sustainability knowledge, and universities responsible for implementing sustainability policies.

This distinction is made because both parties play complementary roles. Researchers analyze sustainability perceptions, design educational content, and identify knowledge gaps. Universities integrate sustainability into the curriculum, implement structural changes, and support campus-wide sustainability projects.

In this study, “university” includes not only academic administration but also all institutional mechanisms that drive sustainability policies (faculty committees, student councils, and sustainability offices).

6.2 Researchers' tasks

6.2.1 *In-depth analysis and review*

This study demonstrated that students predominantly associate sustainability with environmental and social dimensions, while economic and cultural sustainability remain secondary. Further research should explore the reasons behind this perception, particularly within different disciplines. Longitudinal studies could assess the impact of existing sustainability initiatives in Turkish universities and track improvements over time.

In doing so, researchers may consider regional institutional disparities, as sustainability awareness levels can vary widely between universities in metropolitan areas and those in underfunded rural regions.

6.2.2 *Educational program development*

Findings indicate that students struggle to grasp sustainability holistically. Therefore, researchers should focus on designing education modules that integrate sustainability into discipline-specific contexts. For instance, in engineering faculties, sustainability should be incorporated into project-based learning activities where students develop real-world solutions for energy efficiency or waste reduction in their universities.

6.2.3 *Targeted awareness initiatives*

Instead of broad awareness campaigns, sustainability initiatives should be designed based on students' specific misconceptions and knowledge gaps. For example, considering that economic sustainability was the least understood dimension in this study, targeted workshops on circular economy models and sustainable business practices could be introduced particularly in collaboration with regional chambers of commerce and industrial zones such as those in Kocaeli, Gaziantep, or Kayseri, where sustainable industry practices are increasingly being promoted.

6.2.4 *Duties of universities*

1. ***Curriculum Integration with a Practical Focus:*** Sustainability education should not remain theoretical but should be embedded in courses with practical applications. For instance, social sciences departments could introduce service-learning projects where students work with local communities on sustainability challenges, while architecture and engineering students could collaborate on designing sustainable

campus infrastructure. In the context of this change in the curriculum and building a sustainable campus, the development of the nature quotient (NQ), the capacity of students to perceive, process and organize information about ecological connections, is supported by the creation of knowledge environments such as climate fiction (cli-fi). The development of NQ also promotes the development of an eco-plus culture. This is a paradigm that transforms the perception of the environment into policies and everyday behavior [107, 109].

2. **Campus-Based Sustainability Projects:** Instead of generic sustainability policies, universities should implement student-led sustainability projects. Based on the findings of this study, universities in Turkey should establish campus sustainability hubs where students can actively participate in energy conservation, recycling programs, or urban farming initiatives.
3. **Community Partnerships and Industry Collaboration:** To bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, universities should collaborate with municipalities, non-governmental organizations, and local businesses.
4. **Institutionalizing Sustainability Beyond Infrastructure:** While investments in green buildings and renewable energy are essential, universities should also focus on embedding sustainability into institutional decision-making processes. This includes ensuring that student representatives have formal roles in sustainability committees—a practice that remains limited in many Turkish universities but is critical for participatory governance.
5. **Community Partnerships and Industry Collaboration:** To bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, universities should collaborate with municipalities, non-governmental organizations, and local businesses. Joint projects such as sustainable urban planning, local biodiversity conservation, or energy transition programs would enable students to apply sustainability concepts in real-world scenarios.
6. **Institutionalizing Sustainability Beyond Infrastructure:** While investments in green buildings and renewable energy are essential, universities should also focus on embedding sustainability into institutional decision-making processes. For example, student councils should have formal representation in sustainability committees, ensuring that student perspectives shape university policies.

This includes ensuring that student representatives have formal roles in sustainability committees—a practice that remains limited in many Turkish universities but is critical for participatory governance.

By shifting from broad sustainability advocacy to concrete, action-oriented strategies, Turkish universities can cultivate a generation of graduates who not only understand sustainability in theory but also apply it effectively within their communities and future careers.

Supplementary Information

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Supplementary Material 1.

Supplementary Material 2.

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Author contributions

All authors of this study have contributed to the preparation and writing process of the article as follows: [Esra Kızıloğlu]: Developing the research idea, literature review and writing the first draft of the article. [Esra Kızıloğlu]: Managing the data collection process, analysing the data and interpreting the results. [Emine Nihan Cici Karaboga]: Methodological design, editing the manuscript and revising the final version. [Emine Nihan Cici Karaboga]: Conducting ethical approval processes. All authors gave a joint approval of the results and contents of the study.

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Data availability

"The datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study (including survey responses and interview transcripts) are not publicly available due to participant confidentiality. Aggregated data are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request."

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The interview procedure of this study was approved by the Selçuk University Ethics Committee and followed the relevant guidelines. Informed consent for participation was obtained from all participants.

Consent to publish

NA.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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References

1. Abd-Razak MZ, Mustafa NKF, Che-Ani AI, Abdullah NAG, Mohd-Nor MFI. Campus sustainability: student's perception on campus physical development planning in Malaysia. *Proc Eng.* 2011;20:230–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2011.11.160>.
2. Abdulrazzaq ZM, Al-Abdaly HM, Ahmad MD. The sustainable campus - University of Anbar as model. *InAIP Conference Proceeding.* 2024;72:020015. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0181572>.
3. Abubakar I, Al-Shihri F, Ahmed S. Students' assessment of campus sustainability at the university of dammam. *Saudi Arabia Sustain.* 2016;8(1):59. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8010059>.
4. Adams R, Martin S, Boom K. University culture and sustainability: Designing and implementing an enabling framework. *J Clean Prod.* 2018;171:434–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.032>.
5. Adenle YA, Abdul-Rahman M, Soyinka OA. Exploring the usage of social media in extant campus sustainability assessment frameworks for sustainable campus development. *Int J Sustain High Educ.* 2022;23(1):135–58.
6. Adenle YA, Chan EH. Exploring the utilisation of theoretical basis in existing campus sustainability appraisal tools. *Int J Higher Edu Sustain.* 2021;3(3):165–86.
7. Adeoye-Olatunde OA, Olenik NL. Research and scholarly methods: Semi-structured interviews. *J Am Coll Clin Pharm.* 2021;4(5):1358–67. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jac5.1441>.
8. Alam, I. (2018). *A sustainable campus for the higher education institutions in the US* (Master's thesis, Iowa State University).
9. Almeida PS, Lopes AS, Oliveira BD. Sustainability in university campuses and environmental education policy: complementary governance toward consciousness structure in carbon emissions reductions. *Towards Green Campus Operations: Energy, Climate and Sustainable Development Initiatives at Universities*; 2018. p. 197–204.
10. Alsharif MA. The structural modelling of significant organisational and individual factors for promoting sustainable campus in Saudi Arabia. *Front Sustain.* 2024;5:1231468.
11. Amaral LP, Martins N, Gouveia JB. Quest for a sustainable university: a review. *Int J Sustain High Educ.* 2015;16(2):155–72. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-02-2013-0017>.
12. Anantsuksomsri S, Positlimpakul K, Chatakul P, Janpathompong D, Chen G, Tontisirin N. Carbon sequestration analysis of the university campuses in the Bangkok Metropolitan Region. *J Infrastruct Policy Dev.* 2024;8(6):3385.
13. Barbier EB. The concept of sustainable economic development. *Environ Conserv.* 1987;14(2):101–10.
14. Barth M, Godemann J, Rieckmann M, Stoltenberg U. Developing key competencies for sustainable development in higher education. *Int J Sustain High Educ.* 2007;8(4):416–30. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14676370710823582>.
15. Battistini R, Passarini F, Marrollo R, Lantieri C, Simone A, Vignali V. How to assess the carbon footprint of a large university? The case study of university of bologna's Multicampus organization. *Energies.* 2022;16(1):166.
16. Belina A. Semi-structured interviewing as a tool for understanding informal civil society. *Volunt Sector Rev.* 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1332/204080522x16454629995872>.
17. Beringer J, Adomßent M. Higher education for sustainable development: a case study of the university of Lüneburg. *Environ Educ Res.* 2008;14(5):593–608.
18. Boström M. A missing pillar? Challenges in theorizing and practicing social sustainability. *Sustain Sci Pract Pol.* 2012;8(1):3–14.

19. Bozoğlu O, Çiğirim E. Sürdürülebilirlik, Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Sürdürülebilir Üniversiteler. *Socr J Interdisc Soc Stud*. 2022;18:146–58.
20. Braun V, Clarke V. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual Res Psychol*. 2006;3(2):77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>.
21. Brundtland Komisyonu (WCED). (1987). *Our Common Future: Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development (A/42/427)*
22. Byrne, E., Desha, C. J., & Fitzpatrick, J. J. (2013). *Education for sustainability in engineering: A guide and resource for curriculum development*. Routledge.
23. Cameron L. *Metaphor in educational discourse*. Advances in applied linguistics. London: Continuum; 2003.
24. Chourey, V., Mehta, R., & Gautam, S. (2024). GRACIAS – Green resolution in academic campuses for intellectually aware sustainability. In: *2024 1st international conference on cognitive, green and ubiquitous computing (IC-CGU)*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IC-CGU58078.2024.10530787>
25. Clark CR. Collective action competence: an asset to campus sustainability. *Int J Sustain High Educ*. 2016;17(4):559–78. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-04-2015-0073>.
26. Clugston, R. M., & Calder, W. (1999). Critical dimensions of sustainability in higher education. In W. Leal Filho (Ed.), *Sustainability and university life* (pp. 31–46). Peter Lang.
27. Clugston, R.M. and W. Calder (1999). *Critical Dimensions of Sustainability in Higher Education*, in W.L.Filho (ed.), *Sustainability and University Life*. Peter Lang, New York.
28. Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education* (8th ed.). Routledge.
29. Cortese AD. The critical role of higher education in creating a sustainable future. *Plan High Educ*. 2003;31(3):15–22.
30. Creswell JW, Poth CN. *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage; 2018.
31. DeJonckheere M, Vaughn L. Semistructured interviewing in primary care research: a balance of relationship and rigour. *Family Med Comm Health*. 2019;7(2):57. <https://doi.org/10.1136/fmch-2018-000057>.
32. Dempsey N, Bramley G, Power S, Brown C. The social dimension of sustainable development: defining urban social sustainability. *Sustain Dev*. 2011;19(5):289–300. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.417>.
33. Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2011). *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
34. Disterheft A, da Silva F, Caeiro SS, Ramos MR, de Miranda Azeiteiro UM. Environmental management systems (EMS) implementation processes and practices in European higher education institutions— Top-down versus participatory approaches. *J Clean Prod*. 2012;31:80–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.02.034>.
35. Disterheft A, da Silva F, Caeiro S, Ramos MR, de Miranda Azeiteiro UM. Sustainable universities—a study of critical success factors for participatory approaches. *J Clean Prod*. 2015;106:11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.01.030>.
36. Doody O, Noonan M. Preparing and conducting interviews to collect data. *Nurse Res*. 2013;20(5):28–32. <https://doi.org/10.7748/NR2013.05.20.5.28.E327>.
37. Dunlap RE, Van Liere KD. The new environmental paradigm scale: From marginality to worldwide use. *J Environ Educ*. 2008;40(1):3–18.
38. Duxbury N, Jeannotte MS. Culture, sustainability and communities: exploring the myths. *Int J Cult Policy*. 2010;16(2):143–59.
39. Elkington, J. (1997). *Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business*. Capstone, Oxford.
40. Fachrudin HT, Fachrudin KA. The relationship between green behaviour and green campus principles: a literature review. *IOP Conf Ser Mater Sci Eng*. 2021;1122:012028. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1122/1/012028>.
41. Fachrudin HT, Fachrudin KA, Utami W. Education activities to realize green campus. *Asian Soc Sci*. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ASS.V15N8P38>.
42. Farag K, Aktas CB. A survey of the most prevalent sustainability initiatives at universities. *Int J Sustain High Educ*. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-07-2023-0285>.
43. Fenner RA, Ainger CM, Cruickshank HJ, Guthrie PM. Embedding sustainable development at Cambridge university engineering department. *Int J Sustain High Educ*. 2005;6(3):229–41. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14676370510607271>.
44. Ferreira JG, de Matos M, Silva H, Franca A, Duarte P. Sustainable campus: the experience of the university of Lisbon at IST. *Sustainability*. 2021;13(14):8050. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13148050>.
45. Gandasari I, Hotimah O, Miyarsah M. Green campus as a concept in creating sustainable campuses. *KnE Soc Sci*. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v4i14.7853>.
46. Giddings B, Hopwood B, O'Brien G. Environment, economy and society: fitting them together into sustainable development. *Sustain Dev*. 2002;10(4):187–96.
47. Giesenbauer B, Müller-Christ G. University 4.0: promoting the transformation of higher education institutions toward sustainable development. *Sustainability*. 2020;12(8):3371. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083371>.
48. Goodland R. The concept of environmental sustainability. *Ann Rev Ecol System*. 1995;1:1–24.
49. Griggs D, Stafford-Smith M, Gaffney O, Rockström J, Öhman MC, Shyamsundar P, Noble I. Sustainable development goals for people and planet. *Nature*. 2013;495(7441):305–7.
50. Gu Y, Wang H, Xu J, Wang Y, Wang X, Robinson ZP, Li F, Wu J, Tan J, Zhi X. Quantification of interlinked environmental footprints on a sustainable university campus: a nexus analysis perspective. *Appl Energy*. 2019;246:65–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.04.015>.
51. Hawkes, J. (2001). The fourth pillar of sustainability: Culture's essential role in public planning. *Common Ground*. https://www.konhaber.com/guncel/musiad_konya_baskani_ulular_konya_icin_2042_yilinda_avrupa_nin_ilk_karbon_no_tr_sehri_olmasi_hedefini_koyduk-1961131h Data of access: 9.03.2025
52. Islam MS, Liu G, Xu D, Chen Y, Li H, Chen C. University-campus-based zero-carbon action plans for accelerating the zero-carbon city transition. *Sustainability*. 2023;15(18):13504.
53. Jarratt D. A comparison of two alternative interviewing techniques used within an integrated research design: a case study in outshopping using semi-structured and non-directed interviewing techniques. *Mark Intell Plan*. 1996;14(6):6–15. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02634509610131108>.
54. John IB, Adekunle SA, Aigbavboa CO. Adoption of circular economy by construction industry SMEs: organisational growth transition study. *Sustainability*. 2023;15(7):5929. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15075929>.

56. Kallio H, Pietilä AM, Johnson M, Kangasniemi M. Systematic methodological review: developing a framework for a qualitative semi-structured interview guide. *J Adv Nurs*. 2016;72(12):2954–65. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13031>.
57. Kaya A. Kentsel karbon politikaları ve üniversitelerin rolü: Türkiye Örneği. *Çevre ve Şehircilik Araştırmaları Dergisi*. 2022;10(3):123–38.
58. Kopnina H. Metaphors of nature and sustainability: Exploring the role of language in developing ecological consciousness. *Environ Educ Res*. 2014;20(4):541–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2013.837575>.
59. Kundu K. Sustainable and sustainable development. In: Madhu NR, Behara BK, editors. *A basic overview of environment and sustainable development*. International Academic Publishing House; 2022. p. 92–7.
60. Kurnalı, M. (2024). Sürdürülebilir Kentler İçin Bir Başlangıç Noktası Olarak Net Sıfır Karbon Küçük Ev (Tiny House) Köyleri. *Kent Akademisi*, 17(Sürdürülebilir İnsani Kalkınma ve Kent), 68–83. <https://doi.org/10.35674/kent.1501154>
61. Kvale, S., & Brinkmann, S. (2009). *InterViews: Learning the Craft of Qualitative Research Interviewing*. SAGE Publications.
62. Lakoff G, Johnson M. *Metaphors We Live By*. University of Chicago Press; 1980.
63. Leal Filho W, Brandli LL, Lange Salvia AL, Rayman-Bacchus L, Azeiteiro UM. The role of universities in achieving the sustainable development goals: recognising, reporting and reconfiguring. *J Clean Prod*. 2019;233:1003–11.
64. Lincoln YS, Guba EG. *Naturalistic inquiry*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage; 1985.
65. Lozano R. Incorporation and institutionalization of SD into universities: Breaking through barriers to change. *J Clean Prod*. 2010;18(7):787–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2009.09.022>.
66. Lozano R, Lukman R, Lozano FJ, Huisingsh D, Lambrechts W. Declarations for sustainability in higher education: becoming better leaders, through addressing the university system. *J Clean Prod*. 2013;48:10–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.10.006>.
67. Mashuri S, Rasak MSA, Alhabsyi F, Syam H. Semi-structured interview: a methodological reflection on the development of a qualitative research instrument in educational studies. *Int J Qual Methods*. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069241247474>.
68. Mendoza JMF, Gallego-Schmid A, Azapagic A. A methodological framework for the implementation of circular economy thinking in higher education institutions: towards sustainable campus management. *J Clean Prod*. 2019;226:831–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.060>.
69. Miles MB, Huberman AM. *Qualitative data analysis: an expanded sourcebook*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage; 1994.
70. Miller TR. Constructing sustainability science: emerging perspectives and research trajectories. *Sustain Sci*. 2013;8(2):279–93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-012-0180-6>.
71. Msengi IG, Doe RK, Wilson CM, Msengi C. Assessing students' attitudes toward campus sustainability at a minority-serving institution in texas. *Sustainability*. 2019;11(24):7083. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11247083>.
72. Msengi I, Doe R, Wilson T, Fowler D, Wigginton C, Olorunyomi S, Banks I, Morel R. Assessment of knowledge and awareness of "sustainability" initiatives among college students. *Renew Energy Environ Sustain*. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1051/REES/2019003>.
73. Mulder KF. Engineering education in sustainable development: sustainability as a tool to open up the engineering mind. *J Clean Prod*. 2006;14(9–11):787–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2005.12.022>.
74. Murray J. Student activism with sustainability in higher education. *J Teach Learn Proc Celebr Schol Res Art Work*. 2016;4(2):23.
75. Newman L, Dale A. Limits to growth rates in an ethereal economy. *Futures*. 2008;40(3):261–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2007.08.017>.
76. Nguyen MH. How can satirical fables offer us a vision for sustainability? *Vis Sustain*. 2024;23:11267. <https://doi.org/10.1313/5/2384-8677/11267>.
77. Nurse, K. (2006). Culture as the fourth pillar of sustainable development. UNESCO Discussion Paper. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000155747>
78. Olszak E. Composite indicators for a sustainable campus—Design rationale and methodology: the case of the Catholic Institute of Lille. *Ecol Ind*. 2012;23:573–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2012.05.021>.
79. Orr, D. W. (1992). *Ecological literacy: Education and the transition to a postmodern world*. State University of New York Press.
80. Osmond, P. (2013). *Greening universities toolkit: Transforming universities into green and sustainable campuses*. United Nations Environment Programme.
81. Patton MQ. *Qualitative research and evaluation methods*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage; 2002.
82. Pereira Ribeiro JM, Hoeckesfeld L, Dal Magro CB, Favretto J, Barichello R, Lenzi FC, Secchi L, Montenegro de Lima CR, Osório S, de Andrade Guerra JB. Green campus Initiatives as sustainable development dissemination at higher education institutions: Students' perceptions. *J Clean Prod*. 2021;312:127671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127671>.
83. Posner SM, Stuart R. Understanding and advancing campus sustainability using a systems framework. *Int J Sustain High Educ*. 2013;14(3):264–77.
84. Qian F, Yang L. Green campus environmental design based on sustainable theory. *J Clean Energy Technol*. 2018;6(2):159–64. <https://doi.org/10.18178/JOCET.2018.6.2.453>.
85. Rands GP, Starik M. The short and glorious history of sustainability in North American management education. In: Wankel C, Stoner JAF, editors. *Management education for global sustainability*. Information Age Publishing; 2009. p. 19–49.
86. Redclift M. Sustainable development (1987–2005): An oxymoron comes of age. *Sustain Dev*. 2005;13(4):212–27. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.281>.
87. Ribeiro F, Veiga L, Santos D. Sustainable campuses: Promoting students' awareness and proactivity in sustainable development. *Sustainability*. 2021;13(4):2045. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042045>.
88. Ribeiro J, Hoeckesfeld L, Magro C, Favretto J, Barichello R, Lenzi F, Secchi L, Lima C, Guerra J. Green Campus Initiatives as sustainable development dissemination at higher education institutions: Students' perceptions. *J Clean Prod*. 2021;312:127671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.127671>.
89. Ribeiro J, Hoeckesfeld L, Magro C, Favretto J, Barichello R, Lenzi F, Secchi L, Lima C, Guerra J. Green Campus Initiatives as sustainable development dissemination at higher education institutions: Students' perceptions. *J Clean Prod*. 2021;312:127671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.127671>.
90. Sachs JD. From millennium development goals to sustainable development goals. *The lancet*. 2012;379(9832):2206–11.

91. Schmitt R. Systematic metaphor analysis as a method of qualitative research. *Qual Res.* 2005;5(3):359–78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794105056923>.
92. Segalas J, Ferrer-Balas D, Mulder KF. What do engineering students learn in sustainability courses? The effect of the pedagogical approach. *J Clean Prod.* 2010;18(3):275–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2009.09.015>.
93. Sezen-Gültekin G, Argon T. Metaphor analysis as a research method in educational sciences: contributions and challenges. *Edu Res Rev.* 2022;17(6):255–68.
94. Shepard J, Johnson L. Implementing sustainable institutional practices. *J Educ Sustain Dev.* 2009;3(2):217–20. <https://doi.org/10.1177/097340820900300220>.
95. Silverman D. *Interpreting qualitative data.* London: Sage; 2015.
96. Soini K, Birkeland I. Exploring the scientific discourse on cultural sustainability. *Geoforum.* 2014;51:213–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2013.12.001>.
97. Sterling, S. (2001). Sustainable education: re-visioning learning and change. *Schumacher Briefings*
98. Sterling, S. (2010). *Sustainability education: perspectives and practice across higher education.* Routledge
99. Swaim JA, Maloni MJ, Napshin SA, Henley AB. Influences on student intention and behavior toward environmental sustainability. *J Bus Ethics.* 2014;124(3):465–84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-1883-zphilpapers.org>.
100. Thompson R, Green W. When sustainability is not priority: an analysis of trends and strategies. *Int J Sustain High Educ.* 2005;6(1):7–17.
101. Throsby D. On the sustainability of cultural capital. *Camb J Econ.* 2005;29(3):227–36. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cje/bei051>.
102. Tilbury, D. (2011). Education for sustainable development: an expert review of processes and learning. UNESCO
103. Too L, Bajracharya B. Sustainable campus: engaging the community in sustainability. *Int J Sustain High Educ.* 2015;16:57–71. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-07-2013-0080>.
104. Tutar H. Nitel arařtırmalarda geçerlilik ve güvenilirlik: Metafor analizi ve görüşme yöntemleri. *Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi.* 2022;22(2):117–40.
105. UNESCO. (2020). Education for sustainable development: A roadmap. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374802>
106. Velazquez L, Munguia N, Platt A, Taddei J. Sustainable university: what can be the matter? *J Clean Prod.* 2006;14(9–11):810–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2005.12.008>.
107. Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. Exploring the role of rejection in scholarly knowledge production: Insights from granular interaction thinking and information theory. *Learned Publ.* 2024;37(4):e1636. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1636>.
108. Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird.* AISDL. <https://books.google.com/books?id=N10jEQAAQBAJ>
109. Vuong, Q.-H., & Nguyen, M.-H. (2025). *On Nature Quotient.* Working Papers CEB 25–003. ULB– Université Libre de Bruxelles.
110. Waas T, Verbruggen A, Brezet H. Universities and sustainable development: a review of the contribution of universities to education for sustainable development, research for sustainable development and university operations. *J Clean Prod.* 2011;19(18):1801–15.
111. Walker, P., & Mendler, S. (2017). *Creating a Sustainable Campus from the Ground up* (pp. 307–327). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-47895-1_19
112. Wang Q, Feng X, Tian B, Chen Y. Green campus culture construction of green university. *Adv Mater Res.* 2013;869–870:980–5. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.869-870.980x>.
113. Wang R, Liu Y, Xu H. Building green culture in universities: The role of sustainable campus practices. *J Clean Prod.* 2013;46:112–9.
114. Washington-Ottombre C, Bigalke S. An aggregated and dynamic analysis of innovations in campus sustainability. *Int J Sustain High Educ.* 2018;19(2):353–75. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-05-2017-0071>.
115. World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED). (1987, 4 Ağustos). Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future
116. World Commission on Environment and Development. (1987). *Our common future.* Oxford University Press.
117. Wright T. University presidents' conceptualizations of sustainability in higher education. *Int J Sustain High Educ.* 2010;11(1):61–73. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14676371011010057>.
118. Wu, D. (2015). A student-participation approach to attaining sustainability on campus. *SpringerPlus*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2193-1801-4-S2-P8>.
119. Yasin G, Shoaib M, Nawaz MF, Aziz S, Azhar MF, Imtiaz MT, Gul S. Assessing the role of public institutions in carbon sequestration through woody vegetation under arid conditions: a case study of Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan. *Pakistan Pak J Bot.* 2024;56(5):1831–40.
120. Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (1999). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel arařtırma yöntemleri.* Seçkin Yayıncılık.
121. Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2018). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel arařtırma yöntemleri* (11. baskı). Seçkin Yayıncılık.
122. Yuan X, Zuo J, Huisingh D. Green universities in China—what matters? *J Clean Prod.* 2013;61:36–45.

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